

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office
2800 Cottage Way, Suite W-2605
Sacramento, California 95825-1846
SFWO_mail@fws.gov

In Reply Refer to:
2022-0022617

November 8, 2022

Regulatory Division Chief
Attn: Greg Brown
Department of the Army
San Francisco District, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, California 94102
gregory.g.brown@usace.army.mil

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3 from the Bay Area Rapid Transit (BART) Weir to the Union Pacific Railroad (UPRR) Bridge in the City of Fremont, Alameda County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers [Corps] file number 2011-00420S)

Dear Regulatory Division Chief:

This letter is in response to the Corps' November 4, 2021, request for initiation of consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3 (proposed project) from the BART weir to the UPRR bridge in the City of Fremont, Alameda County, California. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*), threatened Pacific Coast population Distinct Population Segment of the western snowy plover (western snowy plover) (*Charadrius nivosus nivosus*), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹, and proposed endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of longfin smelt (longfin smelt) (*Spirinchus thaleichthys*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402). Critical habitat has been designated for the California red-legged frog and western snowy plover but does not occur within the action area.

The federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps issuing a permit to the Alameda County Flood Control District (District) pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*) and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*) to conduct channel maintenance and restoration on a 5.6-mile-

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

long reach of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel, from the BART weir at the upstream end to 600 feet downstream of the UPRR bridge at the downstream end in the City of Fremont, Alameda County, California. Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog and may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse, California clapper rail, western snowy plover, and San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of longfin smelt.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following:

- 1) The October 2022 *Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project, City of Fremont, Alameda County, California Biological Assessment for USFWS Consultation* (District 2022);
- 2) The June 2022 *Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project- Phases 1 and 2 Alameda County, California* (Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan) (Questa Engineering Corporation 2022);
- 3) Communications among the Service, the Corps, the District, Environmental Collaborative, Questa Engineering Corporation, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration/National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), and California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW); and
- 4) Other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail because: (1) these species are unlikely to occur in the proposed project footprint for the creek restoration project due to the lack of suitable tidal marsh habitat; (2) the implementation of water quality best management practices (BMPs) and bypassing stream flows downstream will avoid the potential for the contamination or degradation of tidal marsh habitat downstream; (3) the changes in sediment loads and downstream deposition (estimated at an average of 1 inch of sediment deposition on the tidal floodplain each year) are not expected to have any substantial adverse effects on tidal marsh habitat in the tidal reach of the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel and are expected to benefit the accretion of tidal marsh habitat along the sediment-starved reach in the long-term; (4) the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail are unlikely to occur in the construction footprint of the temporary soil storage/wetland creation site due to the lack of suitable vegetative cover; (5) salt marsh harvest mouse-proof wildlife exclusion fencing plus a 5-foot unvegetated buffer will be placed between the temporary soil storage/wetland creation site and adjacent suitable pickleweed habitat; (6) before any vegetation removal at the temporary soil storage/wetland creation site, a qualified biologist will search for any potential salt marsh harvest mouse nests; (7) a 50-foot buffer will be maintained around any potential salt marsh harvest mouse nests until a qualified biologist has determined that the young are independent of the nest; (8) vegetation at the temporary soil storage/wetland creation site will be removed using only hand tools; (9) all trash that could attract predators will be removed from the site; (10) the salt marsh harvest mouse will benefit from the creation of 5 acres of suitable salt marsh habitat at the wetland creation site; (11) California clapper rails have not been observed during surveys conducted between 2010 and 2021 along the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel near the soil storage/wetland creation site since 2011 when only a single California clapper rail was detected suggesting that California clapper rails only infrequently disperse along the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel near the

soil storage/wetland creation site and are unlikely to breed near there (Olofson Environmental Inc. 2015, 2016, 2018a, 2018b, 2020, 2021, and 2022); and (12) tidal marsh habitat for the California clapper rail in the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel would be visually screened by the north levee from work at the soil storage/wetland creation site.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the western snowy plover because: (1) implementation of water quality BMPs and requirements to bypass all creek surface water flows downstream will avoid degradation of tidal marsh foraging habitat along the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel downstream of the proposed project; (2) no western snowy plover nests have been observed within 600 feet of the soil storage/wetland creation site during surveys conducted in suitable salt pond nesting habitat at the nearby Eden Landing Ecological Reserve in 2015-2020; (3) preconstruction surveys will be conducted by a qualified biologist near the temporary soil storage/wetland creation site during the western snowy plover's March 1 – September 15 breeding season; (4) a 600-foot buffer will be maintained from any nesting western snowy plovers until the young have fledged as determined by a qualified biologist; and (5) all trash that could attract predators will be removed from the site.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of longfin smelt because: (1) the implementation of water quality BMPs, use of cofferdams to isolate construction sites and contain construction materials, and bypassing stream flows downstream will avoid the potential for the contamination or degradation of aquatic habitat for the longfin smelt; (2) no diversion facilities will be installed that could entrain longfin smelt; (3) no longfin smelt are expected to be present between June 1 and October 31 at the origin of the bypass pipe required to be used during channel dewatering and construction; (4) limiting channel dewatering and in-channel construction to between June 1 and October 31 will effectively avoid potential adverse effects to all life stages of longfin smelt, including spawning, egg incubation, larval dispersal, and juvenile rearing; (5) avoiding construction during times of year when longfin smelt would potentially be spawning and larvae rearing in the downstream tidal areas; and (6) limiting construction to the summer and early fall when instream flows in the creek are naturally lowest and seasonal water temperatures are elevated to a level that juvenile rearing habitat is unsuitable for longfin smelt. This represents the Service's conference report on the proposed endangered longfin smelt.

The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California red-legged frog.

Consultation History

March 11, 2021: The Service attended an interagency pre-application meeting for the proposed project with the Corps, the District, and other regulatory agencies.

April 13, 2021: The Service attended a meeting for the proposed project with the Corps, the District, and other regulatory agencies.

November 4, 2021: The San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service received from the Corps the request for informal consultation.

January 11, 2022: The San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service confirmed review of the biological assessment from the Corps and submitted a request for additional information concurrently. The clarifications were

primarily to request materials with more detail on current and past iterations of the larger proposed project implementation.

- March 3, 2022: The Corps responded with copies of the preceding phases' biological assessments, as well as clarification from the District regarding timing and activities.
- July 7, 2022: The San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service submitted an additional request for information to get clarification on the timing and specific actions comprising the proposed project's phased approach.
- July 21, 2022: The Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service received a copy of the biological assessment and the Corps' request for consultation. The Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service recommended conservation measures for the California red-legged frog and the initiation of formal consultation on the California red-legged frog. Environmental Collaborative agreed to revise the biological assessment and the conclusion to likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog pending approval from the Corps.
- August 23, 2022: The San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office and Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office of the Service attended a meeting with the Corps to discuss (1) which phases of the proposed project should be covered under the consultation, (2) the Service's recommendation to formally consult on the California red-legged frog, (3) conservation measures for the California red-legged frog, and (4) revising the effects analysis for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse in the biological assessment. The Corps agreed to formally consult on the California red-legged frog and requested that the District revise the biological assessment.
- August 29, 2022: The Corps provided the Service the Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan. The Service asked if the temporary soil storage and wetland creation proposed in the Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan would be covered under the current consultation for the proposed project or a separate section 7 consultation. The Service also asked whether the Corps had made a determination on the effects of the temporary soil storage and wetland creation on the salt marsh harvest mouse, California clapper rail, and western snowy plover.
- August 31, 2022: The Service received from Questa Environmental Corporation the project plans and avoidance measures for the offsite wetland creation mitigation site. The Corps informed the Service that the current consultation for the proposed project will cover the offsite wetland creation mitigation site. The Service recommended preconstruction surveys for western snowy plovers and maintaining a 600-foot buffer from any western snowy plover nests.
- September 20, 2022: The Service received from the Corps the revised plans for the wetland mitigation site and conservation measures for the salt marsh harvest mouse.

- October 27, 2022: The Service received the revised Biological Assessment, and the Corps requested to consult on the proposed endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of longfin smelt.
- October 28, 2022: The Service recommended conservation measures to avoid disturbing nesting western snowy plovers and California clapper rails.
- October 31, 2022: Environmental Collaborative provided a map of western snowy plover nest locations in salt pond nesting habitat near the proposed soil storage/wetland creation site in 2015-2020 at the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve showing that all nests were more than 600 feet from proposed project construction. Environmental Collaborative provided a revised conservation measure for conducting preconstruction surveys and avoiding the disturbance of nesting western snowy plovers. Environmental Collaborative corrected the Biological Assessment to state that California black rail instead of California clapper rail was observed within one mile of the downstream end of the proposed project in 2012 and provided the negative survey results from 2012. The Service noted based on surveys conducted along the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel between 2010 and 2021 that the California clapper rail was last observed near the soil storage/wetland creation site in 2011 (Olofson Environmental Inc. 2015, 2016, 2018a, 2018b, 2020, 2021, and 2022). Environmental Collaborative also provided a topographic map showing that the north levee would visually screen work activities at the soil storage/wetland mitigation site from tidal marsh habitat along the Alameda Creek Flood Control channel where California clapper rails could potentially occur.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project involves the District implementing restoration activities in the existing Corps-constructed Flood Control Channel along Lower Alameda Creek (Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel). The proposed project reach extends approximately 5.6 miles (29,730 feet) within the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel between the BART weir fish ladder at the upstream end to 600 feet downstream of the UPRR crossing at the downstream end (Figure 1). The proposed project also includes a soil storage area on the north side of the channel levee and west of Union City Boulevard which will continue to be used for soil storage and a portion of which will be converted to salt marsh habitat to provide wetland mitigation for the proposed project (Figure 2).

Restoration activities in the proposed project consist of:

1. Optimizing the existing low flow channel within the approximately 230-foot-wide flood control channel from the scour pool immediately downstream of the BART weir to about 600 feet downstream of the UPRR crossing;
2. Modifying the Rubber Dam #2/Larinier fishway concrete structure and modification of existing grade control (GC) structures;

3. Modifying bridge footings in the channel;
4. Modifying UPRR bridge footings in the channel;
5. Protecting the Pacific Gas and Electric Company (PG&E) gas main channel crossing upstream of the UPRR;
6. Installing new modified GC structures;
7. Installing boulders and large woody structures to improve habitat; and
8. Planting native shrubs and grasses on the configured channel terrace between the levees.

Figure 1. Proposed project area (copied from Figure 16 in District (2022)).

The purpose of the proposed project is to remove migratory impediments and improve the migratory corridor below the BART weir to allow federally threatened Central California Coast steelhead and other fish movement within the flood control channel to access upstream spawning grounds and juvenile rearing habitat. The proposed project is designed to optimize sediment transport while maintaining the original Corps design for containment and conveyance of flood flows with a minimum requirement of levee freeboard.

Optimizing sediment transport downstream through the proposed project reach will thereby reduce maintenance desilting frequency of the flood control channel as required under the Corps' Operation & Maintenance (O&M) Manual, greatly diminishing the routine disturbance to marsh habitat that has become established along the bottom of the flood control channel. Lower Alameda Creek is currently considered to have a net sediment deficit and is susceptible to conversion of low marsh habitat to open water habitat with sea level rise. This is sometimes referred to as "marsh drowning." The proposed project will assist in abating this condition to the benefit of species that occur in the tidal reach.

The Phase 1 area is located from the BART weir to Rubber Dam #2, and Phase 2 extends downstream to the Dry Creek confluence. Phase 3 extends from above Decoto Road to 600 feet downstream of the UPRR crossing with some overlap and reworking of the lower Phase 2 channel to enable a better match of final low flow channel grades between the phases. Phase 3 is currently unfunded, but preliminary design and environmental work have been completed for this phase.

The proposed project includes improvements to optimize and realign the existing low-flow channel for sediment transport by excavating accumulated sediment to create a trapezoidal low-flow channel ("sediment transport channel") fully contained within the existing Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel. The top elevation of the sediment transport channel will conform to the channel's existing flood terrace (main channel) elevation, which is at about the two-year flow line. The proposed sediment transport channel segment longitudinal profile will be steepened to assist sediment movement. Nestled within the sediment transport channel will be a fish passage channel ("fish passage channel") designed for 5 cubic feet per second minimum flows. Existing GC structures will be modified to eliminate barriers and impediments to fish passage and to maintain the proposed channel improvements. The Rubber Dam #2 GC structure has already been modified for fish passage but will be further enhanced.

The proposed project will be constructed in multiple phases as described below in order to complete each phase within the permitted in-water work window (June 1 - October 31) as funding becomes available. Currently the plan is to construct the proposed project in two phases (1 and 2) during the summer/fall of 2023 and 2024. Phase 3 is currently being designed, but is not funded.

Sediment Transport Channel and Fish Passage Channel

The new sediment transport channel will be constructed to generally meander in the center and below the existing invert bottom of the approximately 230-foot-wide Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel. It closely follows the existing low flow channel that has naturally established within the originally constructed flat bottomed channel. Historic photogrammetric and geomorphic analysis of this channel indicates it has consistently maintained this alignment over a number of years and appears to be a stable alignment.

To construct, stabilize, and maintain the sediment transport channel cross-sectional dimensions, materials excavated from areas of high sediment deposit will be used to backfill existing highly incised areas of the channel invert bottom and braided arms of the low-flow channel. The cross-sectional geometry of the proposed sediment transport channel will consist of a 24-foot-wide bottom width and 3:1 side slopes (horizontal to vertical). This enhancement will mimic the current naturally established channel meander and sinuosity. At locations where the proposed low-flow channel will be close to the levee toe, rock riprap (buried below grade) will be used to

Figure 2. Soil disposal and wetland habitat mitigation area (copied from Figure 14A in District (2022)).

secure the low-flow channel bank in place, or the existing low-flow channel will be filled either with rock riprap or with excavated sediment, and a new alignment towards the center of the flood control channel will be excavated to connect the up- and downstream segment points of deflection. The undermined levee toe of slope sections will also be armored with rock riprap buried below grade. Within the modified sediment transport channel's 24-foot-wide bottom width, a second fish passage channel with a bottom width of 2 feet by 24 inches deep and top width of 8 feet will be constructed, and it is anticipated that this new active fish passage channel will persist similarly as observed following construction.

The fish passage channel within the project limits will have a minimum depth of 24 inches and be able to pass a minimum flow of 5 to 40 cubic feet per second in support of steelhead migration. The entire reach of the combined sediment/fish channel profile between Rubber Dam #2 and the BART weir will have a decreasing gradient from upstream to downstream with a drop of 3 feet for every 500 feet. This reconfiguration is critical to efficient sediment transport toward the deeper tidal zone further downstream.

Migratory Habitat Enhancements

To assist fish migration, velocity breaks and pools have been incorporated into the design of the low-flow channel. This involves installation of large boulders in the outside bends of the low-flow channel meanders to assist upstream migration during the fall/winter months (October through March). All disturbed areas will be restored and planted with appropriate vegetation that recognizes the flood conveyance constraints of the channel. The reconstructed channel terrace will be revegetated with appropriate plant species (e.g., native grasses and shrubs) that respond to high flows without creating hydraulic obstructions to compromise the levees' integrity. This includes plantings of native perennial forb and grass species and seeding with native annual grass species (e.g., mulefat, creeping wild rye, rough sedge, arroyo lupine, meadow barley, Italian ryegrass, marsh baccharis, iris leaved rush, and spike rush).

Steelhead and other fish and wildlife benefit from habitat complexity and diversity along a stream corridor. As part of a pilot program during the initial phase of the proposed project, physical structures such as log clusters and boulders will be installed adjacent to the low-flow fish passage channel to provide overhead and in-channel cover for migrating and rearing steelhead and other species.

Habitat Heterogeneity

One of the primary driving forces for the restoration project is to improve habitat diversity and aquatic habitat complexity without impacting flood control and sediment transport ability. Increased complexity and heterogeneity will greatly improve the biological value of the reconstructed channel and provide the ecological base that enhances aquatic habitat and helps maintain sufficient flow depth for salmonids in the thalweg of the flood control channel. Initially creating this can be a challenge because this amount of variability cannot easily be constructed by typical earthwork contractors. Complex bed features need to naturally evolve over time, following construction. The proposed channel design provides suitable channel geometry with added habitat enhancement features that will increase bedform variability within the low-flow channel system. The proposed channel configuration and constructed habitat features have been designed to allow the channel to evolve with time and to help to direct the gradual geomorphic evolution to a sustainable stream channel that balances between flood control, channel maintenance requirements, sediment transport, and aquatic habitat improvements.

Thalweg Alignment, Depth and Stability

The low-flow channel design concept includes log structures that will locally increase bed scour so that semi-permanent pools are created and the pool-to-pool connection in the thalweg channel is maintained naturally. The project reach has a modest slope (0.13 percent), and creating pools and streambed variability that will maintain the appropriate depth requires construction of in-channel stable features that cause flow contraction and localized scour. The design needs to avoid creating sudden changes in bed slope such as step pools or J hooks.

The proposed design uses two techniques to accomplish this. The first technique is to create micro-topography on the bottom of the sediment transport channel. This is done by creating the cross channel slope towards the fish passage channel as it meanders back and forth across the bottom of the channel.

The grading generally follows the basic geometry of a point-bar and floodplain and reinforces the meandering nature of a natural channel. The channel is expected to adjust slightly within the first few years as the fish passage channel adjusts and finds its new stable equilibrium. These topographic features also concentrate flow as flow drops through the spring and summer. This grading technique is designed to produce moderate bed scour to help define the channel thalweg.

The second technique is to create localized scour in the apexes of the fish passage channel meanders and other appropriate areas by using woody debris structures. Woody debris plays a key role in creating habitat heterogeneity in this type of low gradient creek. From an ecological standpoint, woody debris can influence the local populations of aquatic organisms at the stream reach scale. Woody debris is integral in the food web for a stream ecosystem. Woody debris provides a habitat for aquatic organisms and modifies other habitats within the stream. The number and spacing of pools or riffles can be influenced by the size and amount of woody debris in the reach.

In a natural system, accumulation of large woody debris often occurs at specific points in a stream. The mid- or downstream end of a meander bend, the head of a side channel, the apex of a bar, pools, or other relatively low energy points often collect woody debris. Habitat features such as scour pools are created and maintained by the localized increase in velocity and associated localized scour.

Significant design elements were added to center around woody debris clusters and generally simulate debris jams that are found naturally in a creek system. The localized scour from these structures will create deeper pool areas that will be connected by the meandering channel and produce a reoccurring series of pools, runs, and riffles within the bottom of the sediment transport channel at flows at or above 3 cubic feet per second. The habitat structures will be a series of interlocking horizontal logs that are pinned in place by vertical wooden piles and connected using threaded steel rods. Horizontal logs will be placed across the fish passage channel to contract flows under the logs, enhancing the expected pier scour that will occur around the vertical piles. By contracting flows in the creek, velocity is locally increased, creating a change in flow state from sub- to supercritical and back again. This is what causes flow vortices and increases local bed scour action to maintain pool depths.

Five different types and orientation of artificial woody debris structures (log structures) have been developed for use in the proposed project. The log structures will be constructed using more or less uniform smooth/rounded logs.

The proposed project will use raw untreated timber logs that are readily available from nearby sources. These logs will be anchored and bolted together in several types of structures containing a varying number of logs. The log structures will be positioned so they will collect channel debris to increase channel cover and therefore reduce salmonid predation potential. The log structures are designed to be over-topped at flows greater than 500 cubic feet per second. Debris caught on the structure at lower flows will float free of the structure at high flows. It is also not anticipated that the log structures will collect any large debris that could potentially break free and impact flood control channel functions or create log jam or scour hazards near or under any existing bridges within the proposed project area.

Typically, each of these structures can be built in four to six hours, with a crew of two laborers, an excavator and operator. Specialized tools for drilling rock and coring logs, as well as construction materials are readily available and are economical to purchase or rent. Mulefat staking will be included in the structure fabrication. These features are juxtaposed on either side of the channel to provide scour and depositional features in the channel bed.

Questa Engineering has proposed substituting the construction of riffles to replace grouted sills that were originally proposed. Grouted sills/GCs are thought to be problematic and may not be acceptable in the creek by the regulatory agencies, so a series of riffles have been incorporated into the design that are generally 50 feet long and have at least a 1 percent gradient drop across them. The upstream and downstream inverts of the riffle are held constant by the use of rock keyways. Riffles are expected to form on their own between the scour pool locations. The riffles are designed to function up to the bankfull discharge flow. Above that elevation, the flow depth is too great and the riffle's impact on higher magnitude flood events is less than significant.

Construction Phasing

The proposed project is to be constructed in three phases depending on permitting and funding availability. Currently Phases 1 and 2 are funded for implementation in 2023-2024. The three phases are briefly described below.

Phase 1. Scour Pool Downstream of BART Weir to Rubber Dam #2

Low Flow Channel: Optimize and realign the existing low-flow channel for sediment transport by excavating accumulated sediment to create a trapezoidal low-flow channel fully contained within the existing Flood Control Channel. The channel will have 3:1 (horizontal to vertical) slopes with top and bottom widths of 78 feet and 24 feet, respectively, and about 10 feet deep. The top elevation of the sediment transport channel will conform to the channel's original designed flat bottom elevation. This sediment transport channel segment horizontal profile will be steepened to assist sediment movement. The fish passage channel that carries 5 cubic feet per second minimum flows will be nestled within the sediment transport channel. The fish passage channel top and bottom width and depth dimensions will be 8 feet by 2 feet by 2 feet deep.

Levee Toe of Slope Repair: Reconstruct an approximately 600-foot section on the outside bend of the eroding south levee toe by excavating and installing rock veins keyed in place to protect against further erosion.

Modification of Rubber Dam #2 (Larinier Fishway): Rubber Dam #2, a former grouted-rock GC structure was modified to support flow diversion operations and subsequently modified to install the Larinier fishway. This 50-foot-wide concrete and the remnant grouted rock structure will be modified by demolishing the middle segment similarly as described below under

Modification of Existing Grade Control (GC) Structures. The modified and reconstructed structure's cross-sectional face will be covered with grouted rock anchored into the channel bottom by two 3-foot-wide grouted rock footings spaced 3 feet apart for stability.

Phase 1 is expected to be completed in a single work period. Approximately 33,432 cubic yards of sediment and soil will be excavated from the channel bottom to create the low-flow channel. Approximately 13,044 cubic yards of sediment will be re-used to fill low spots and braided arms of the low-flow channel (terrace of the new low-flow channel) and compacted. The remaining 20,388 cubic yards will be off-hauled to a local upland storage area for beneficial reuse.

Phase 2: Rubber Dam #2 to Upstream of the Dry Creek Confluence

Phase 2 extends from downstream of the Rubber Dam #2 structure for approximately 8,000 feet to the confluence of Dry Creek downstream and includes modification of GC structures, modification of the bridge footing within the channel, extending the low-flow channel improvements through this reach, and habitat complexity improvements such as installation of boulders and vegetation. The 5,000-foot reach downstream of GC1 is an overlapping transitional zone between Phases 2 and 3. The transition area is designed to minimize sediment deposition as the District seeks funding for Phase 3 and will be regraded during Phase 3 construction consistent with the overall channel design configuration.

Modification of Existing Grade Control (GC) Structures: The four GC Structures, or sills, located downstream of Rubber Dam #2 are spaced at 2,000-foot intervals. Each GC structure consists of two 3-foot thick grouted rock walls 50 feet apart extending to a depth of 9 feet below the channel bottom. The two parallel grouted rock walls extend across the channel width and converge to a 10-foot wide crest elevation above the designed flat channel bottom elevation to prevent head cutting erosion. These structures and transportation bridge crossings have since become impediments to fish migration as the low-flow channel erodes between the structures. The segments immediately upstream and downstream of these structures also accumulate sediment which causes braided shallow channels and sheet flow that adversely affect fish movement.

The GC structures will be modified by cutting out the middle portion (78 feet) to conform to the new low-flow channel width described in Phase 2. The remnant portion of the modified structure on either side of the new low-flow channel will be at the Corps-designed channel bottom elevation. The bottom elevation of the modified structures will conform to the new channel configuration up and downstream. Boulders will be installed up- and downstream of the modified structure adjacent to the new low-flow channel to assist fish migratory habitat complexity development.

Low-Flow Channel Modification at the Transportation and Utility Crossings: All the existing transportation crossings in Phase 2 (Sequoia Terrace and Isherwood Way) and Phase 3 (Decoto Road, Interstate 880, Alvarado Boulevard, and UPRR) within the project limits will be modified for sediment transport and fish passage. The low-flow channel underneath these bridges will be regraded to optimize the low channel width and depth and secured in place with grouted rocks to provide structural stability and prevent braiding.

At each crossing location, the low-flow channel will be constructed to contain the flow volume passing underneath the bridges. At the Interstate 880 and UPRR crossings, the low-flow channel will split between the bridge support columns. One of these channels will be lower than the others in order to serve as the principal corridor for fish movement and sediment. These multiple

channels underneath these bridges will transition approximately 1,000 feet to conform to the existing low-flow channel up- and downstream.

Phase 3. From GC1 to UPRR Crossing

Phase 3 consists of similar improvements as described in Phase 1 and 2. The low-flow channel will be extended through this phase, bridge crossings will be improved, and the PG&E gas main crossing the channel will be protected with grouted rock. One new GC structure similar to the modified structures described above will be installed in the vicinity of the Dry Creek confluence to reduce the anticipated effects of upstream tidal migration after the UPRR crossing improvement is completed.

This phase of construction may not be completed for five to eight years because of current funding constraints. Consequently, the 5,000-foot transition reach downstream of GC1 described under Phase 2 will be regraded to conform to the low-flow channel design.

The District will continue to maintain and monitor the entire Flood Control Channel to assure that the low-flow and other constructed components of the proposed project meet the multi-function goals and objectives of flood protection, sediment transport, and improvement of fish migratory habitat.

Following the completion of the improvements, the District will request modification of the Corps Maintenance Manual to include an adaptive management approach to sustainably meet the flood control channel's competing and contradictory needs and functions.

Soil Storage and Wetland Habitat Mitigation

Sediment excavated from the channel may be stored from one to six months or more on a 2-acre vacant site adjacent to the main channel near the Isherwood Bridge before being transferred to the main soil storage area operated by the Alameda County Water District that is located west of Union City Boulevard and north of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel (see Figure 2). Of this 38-acre area, approximately 5 acres will be used for wetlands mitigation, and 33 acres will be used for temporary soil storage. The vacant site near Isherwood Bridge may also be used as a proposed project laydown, staging, and mobilization area. The main soil storage area is nearly level, currently disturbed, and un-vegetated property. The agreement with Alameda County Water District will be that this area will be restored to existing conditions following cessation of proposed project use.

As indicated in Figure 2 and described above, an approximately 5-acre portion at the west end of the main soil storage area will be converted to salt marsh habitat to provide wetland habitat mitigation to compensate for the permanent impacts of the proposed project. The mitigation area will be located at the western edge of the existing main soil storage area. Wetland habitat will be created by grading existing surface elevations down 0.5 to 1.0 feet to create hydrologic conditions amenable to restoration as a pickleweed-dominated seasonal wetland. This 5-acre area will provide compensatory mitigation for the placement of rock riprap in the flood control channel for levee toe protection, rock protection of GC structures, and bridge scour protection as part of the proposed project. The San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board considers these grouted rock features to be permanent impacts to wetlands/waters of the State, requiring mitigation. The created habitat will be seeded with pickleweed to accelerate wetland establishment and fenced for protection. Appropriate project controls or avoidance and minimization measures will be used to protect existing adjacent pickleweed dominated wetlands

and sensitive species habitat, and a Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan (Questa Engineering Corporation 2022) will be prepared to provide monitoring and ensure successful establishment.

Construction Activities

The District anticipates completion of the proposed improvements over a period of 5-10 years or sooner if grant funds are available. Work in the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel will be limited to the dry season each year to the construction window from June 1 to October 31. However, in-water construction may begin earlier and extend later into the year with agency approval. A one-season period is required for construction of the Phase 1 low-flow channel realignment between the BART weir fishway and Rubber Dam #2. One season is required for the modification of the four existing GC structures and two transportation crossings included in Phase 2. Modification of the transportation crossings in Phase 3 may require five to 10 years to complete. Construction activity will be limited to the daytime only (7:00 AM to 6:00 PM) Monday through Friday.

The sequence of construction and duration of construction of project elements may vary from that presented above. The specific sequence of work will be determined by final engineering design and logistics; availability of grant funding; ability to improve construction efficiencies by scheduling activities concurrently versus sequentially; weather conditions; site space constraints; and compliance with local, state, and federal permitting considerations. Construction will begin as early in the construction window as feasible (when flows are low in the channel) to be able to complete each project element within one construction season and to accommodate potentially overlapping elements. Scheduling may vary, depending on factors such as weather, emergency conditions, and fiscal resources. Construction will occur in phases and may overlap with future phases.

Access to the channel construction sites will be via one of the existing levee maintenance roads/trails, which will be closed to the public near the vicinity of construction activity. The public will be detoured to the levee not in use during active construction. General access to the levee maintenance roads/trails will be along surface streets including Hillview Drive, I Street, Riverwalk Drive, Niles Boulevard, Sequoia Terrace, Isherwood Way, Alvarado Niles Road, Montecito Drive, and Vallejo Street.

Mobilization and isolation of the construction area from the active flow includes:

1. Perform preconstruction surveys, worker training, and other project controls to minimize adverse effects to sensitive resources;
2. Delivery of equipment, materials, temporary buildings, and fencing to the sites;
3. Grading of storage areas as needed;
4. Isolating construction activities in the channel from the active channel utilizing gravel bags, fiber mats, and temporary cofferdams, or other methods, to ensure that fish and aquatic resources will be excluded from the construction area, and that runoff from the construction area will be fully contained during construction activity. The temporary cofferdams may consist of a plastic barrier fence, k-rail barrier, an earthen levee with plastic sheeting to protect it from erosion, interlocking steel sheet-pile and piping for control of water, or another similar type of barrier. Location of these temporary facilities

may be channel spanning or for isolation of smaller localized areas of the project. Flow in the creek will be bypassed around the isolated work area and returned to the low-flow channel downstream of the work area;

5. Native aquatic species in the isolated construction zone will be removed and relocated to the active stream, and the construction area will be dewatered (drained). Fish collection and relocation will follow the standard procedures for fish rescue that have been employed in prior Alameda Creek in-channel construction projects. A fish rescue and relocation plan will be provided as required by NMFS and CDFW. Dewatering of the active construction zone may be on-going; and
6. Construction equipment access to the work area may require a temporary truck and equipment access road from the levee maintenance road/trail into and through the channel. Construction equipment will be needed to work within the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel to access the GC foundations, toe of the levees, grouted riprap placement and low-flow channel construction and material hauling.

Demolition and replacement of existing structures includes:

1. Selective demolition of designated portions of existing GC Structures;
2. Removal of demolition debris from the site; and
3. Disposal of debris at an appropriate landfill or, if feasible, stockpiled for future reuse.

Grading and excavation includes:

1. Grading of the construction sites, channel access roads, and the low-flow channel;
2. Stockpiling and/or removal of materials; and
3. Installation of modified sections of the GC structures below the Corps channel bottom elevation.

In-channel riprap construction, which includes:

1. Hauling of rock to the sites for riprap;
2. Installing sections of rock riprap, including grouting;
3. Boulders; and
4. Cement or slurry trucked to the site.

Backfill includes backfilling of excavated areas and restoration of levee riprap slope used as access to the construction area in the channel.

Site restoration includes:

1. Restoring all disturbed areas to pre-construction condition and removing all temporary dewatering structures;

2. In-kind surface restoration of the recreational trails affected by construction, i.e., aggregates will be added to gravel areas, damaged paved sections will be repaved;
3. Demobilization and final site clean-up; and
4. Planting and seeding with native grasses and perennial forbs on the new low-flow channel floodplain (terraces).

Maintenance Responsibilities

The District owns and is responsible for maintenance of the flood control channel, associated levees and related rock and grouted rock features in the channel. Maintenance associated with these activities will be contained within the active Flood Control Channel and levees from below the BART weir fish way downstream to below the UPRR crossing downstream. Routine maintenance of the channel, including the low-flow channel and GC structures will be conducted under permits authorizing the project construction. These maintenance responsibilities and the monitoring activities summarized below are further described in the updated Corps-approved O&M Plan.

Routine maintenance of the GC structures and the low-flow channel will typically involve:

1. Assessment of the low-flow channel post storms;
2. Removal of trash and large woody debris from the low-flow channel, typically using a combination of hand tools, small cranes and lifts, hoses and suction pumps, and similar small equipment;
3. Periodic visual inspection of the GC structures and low-flow channel;
4. Re-grouting damaged grouted rock (generally following periods of high flow and damage from debris); and
5. Repairs to levee toe damages.

Compliance Monitoring

Compliance monitoring will include the following components:

1. During construction and maintenance, the District will implement the suite of avoidance and minimization measures and BMPs.
2. Water quality data (turbidity) from each construction zone will be monitored downstream of the temporary dams during construction; and
3. The District will prepare and submit annual site monitoring reports, in each year of post-construction of a project element to the regulatory agencies detailing the construction activities and any significant deviations from the proposed project design. Reports will include the most current data available at the time of submittal.

Conservation Measures

The District will implement the following avoidance and minimization measures to avoid and minimize the effects of the proposed project on the California red-legged frog and other special-status species and their habitats:

1. Channel Protection: Isolate in-channel construction areas from the active creek channel with sand bags, fiber mats, cofferdams, or other methods during construction. A detailed dewatering plan will be provided to CDFW and NMFS for review and approval prior to construction.
2. Riparian Vegetation: Access the channel via areas where no or minimal riparian vegetation will be affected.
3. Runoff. Control potential downstream runoff from the construction sites with sand bags, fiber mats, cofferdams, or other methods.
4. Fuel Containment. Fuel and maintain construction equipment out of the channel beyond top of banks. If this is not feasible, containment materials including drip pans or absorbent pads will be used.
5. Concrete Containment. Provide washout areas for vehicles outside of the channel beyond top of banks and isolate these areas to ensure that concrete and grout materials do not runoff into the channel.
6. Equipment Leaks. When working in the channel or where there may be runoff to the channel, ensure that construction equipment will be fitted with absorbent materials at potential fuel, oil, and other fluid leak spots.
7. Spill Containment and Isolation. During construction and post-construction maintenance involving use of equipment in or adjacent to the channel, stockpile sand bags on site so that they may be immediately filled and placed around any spill. In addition, any spills not contained within the maintenance area will immediately be isolated from the active channel.
8. Re-grading. Restore disturbed areas to pre-project contours unless otherwise specified.
9. Monitoring. A qualified biologist will (a) be retained to monitor construction, and (b) will conduct mandatory contractor/worker awareness training for construction personnel if special-status species are found.
10. Site Survey. Prior to construction, the District will provide for a qualified biologist to survey the site to determine whether special-status species are present. Preconstruction surveys will be conducted as necessary for each new phase of construction or where construction has been curtailed for more than 15 calendar days and there remains a potential for dispersal of special-status species into the construction zone. Where necessary, exclusionary fencing will be installed under the supervision of the qualified biologist to isolate construction areas from vegetation to be retained and to prevent special-status species from inadvertently entering the construction zone.

11. Fish Rescue. Following installation of barriers to isolate the construction site from the active channel, a qualified fisheries biologist and team will conduct a fish rescue program for stranded fish prior to initiation of construction activities. Fish removed from the site will be immediately returned to the active channel. A fish rescue and relocation plan will be provided to NMFS and CDFW for review and approval prior to initiating the fish rescue. Lamprey ammocoetes (larval stage of lamprey) drift downstream to areas of low velocity and fine substrates where they burrow, grow, and live as filter feeders for 3-7 years. Standard electrofishing techniques would stun lamprey ammocoetes within their burrows. Since standard electrofishing techniques would not be effective for rescuing lamprey ammocoetes (larval stage of lamprey), electrofishing methods specified in Attachment A of the Bureau of Land Management (2010) *Best Management Practices for Instream Activities to Avoid Adverse Effects to Pacific Lampreys* will be performed within the dewatered zone. Fish removed from site will be returned up or downstream of the temporary dewatered zone.
12. Burrowing Owls. To prevent the risk of burrowing owls from occupying ground squirrel burrows and being inadvertently injured or killed, measures will be taken to minimize the presence of burrows that could be used for retreat by the owls in areas of active construction. If owls are not present, the burrows will be filled to prevent owl retreat or potential nesting only if it conflicts with project activities. If owls are present during the non-nesting season (September 1 through January 31), a qualified biologist, in consultation with CDFW, will passively relocate the owls to avoid any loss of individuals during construction. Burrows will then be filled. Preconstruction surveys and relocation of nonbreeding owls will be ongoing so that no burrowing owls will occur at the proposed construction sites.
13. Western Pond Turtle. Within 15 calendar days prior to construction activities, a qualified biologist will survey for western pond turtles. If turtles are found, the biologist shall relocate the pond turtle to suitable habitat, and an exclusion fence will be installed to prevent movement of turtles back into the construction area.
14. Disturbance of Nesting Birds. Within 15 calendar days prior to construction activities during the bird nesting season (February 1 through August 31), a qualified biologist will survey for raptor and other native bird nests in areas within 500 feet of the proposed construction site. If nesting raptors or other native bird species are found, the District will consult with CDFW to establish appropriate no disturbance buffers around the nest sites and follow-up monitoring to establish a behavioral baseline for the first 24 hours prior to construction and to confirm that any nesting birds are not adversely affected by construction-related disturbance such as noise, vibration, odors and movement of workers or equipment. No construction will be initiated within the sufficient buffers until young have fledged as determined by a qualified biologist. The qualified biologist will have authority to order the cessation of all project activities within a disturbance distance of any active nests if the birds exhibit abnormal nesting behavior which may cause reproductive failure (nest abandonment and loss of eggs and/or young). To address potential for work to affect downstream nesting birds, a qualified biologist will conduct pre-construction surveys of downstream areas to identify nesting by special-status and/or migratory birds. If these species are found nesting within 100 yards of the construction site, the District will consult with CDFW to establish appropriate no disturbance buffers around the nest sites until young have fledged. These buffers will be clearly marked to exclude construction equipment and personnel.

15. Monitoring. The District will visually inspect the low-flow channel and GC structures annually to insure adequate conditions for fish passage. Post-construction low-flow channel longitudinal profile and stream cross-section surveys will be repeated post-construction for two five-year cycles (10 years). As winter flows recede in the spring periods of juvenile steelhead outmigration, to the extent feasible, the District will visually monitor the flood channel margins to determine if juvenile steelhead are present and will ensure that juveniles are not stranded as water surface elevations decline.
16. On-going Measures to Protect Steelhead.
 - a. Routine monitoring at the low-flow channel and GC fishways will include periodic monitoring for debris accumulation and sediment deposits that would impede adult and juvenile migration, and the District will, to the extent feasible, schedule maintenance outside of the period when juveniles and adults may be migrating.
 - b. When maintenance requires isolation of the active channel from the maintenance area, the District will engage a qualified biologist to monitor for the presence of steelhead. If steelhead are found anywhere in the area to be isolated, juvenile steelhead will be captured and released to the active channel downstream of the maintenance area.
 - c. If adult steelhead are in the maintenance area, they will be (a) diverted to the isolated active channel or (b) captured and transported to the reach upstream of Mission Boulevard.
 - d. In an emergency/unplanned maintenance event, the District will notify NMFS and CDFW as soon as possible, and immediately make all feasible and necessary efforts to isolate the maintenance area from the active stream as rapidly as possible.
17. O&M Manual: The NMFS/Service/CDFW-approved O&M Manual for the proposed project will include protocols for performance monitoring and impact avoidance and minimization during O&M. Proposed measures include measures described below.
18. Avoidance and Minimization Measures. For on-going maintenance, the District will apply construction measures, similar to conservation measures 1-14 (above), as detailed in the NMFS/Service/CDFW-approved O&M Manual.
19. Scheduling. To the extent feasible, the District will avoid scheduling maintenance activities in the Flood Control Channel in the period from January 1 through May 31.
20. California Red-legged Frog.
 - a. The District will ensure the Service, CDFW, and/or their designated agents can immediately and without delay, access, and inspect the site for compliance with the project description, conservation measures, and reasonable and prudent measures, and to evaluate project effects to the California red-legged frog and its habitat.

- b. At least 30 calendar days prior to the onset of construction activities, the District shall submit the name(s) and credentials of biologists who would conduct activities specified in the following measures. No project activities shall begin until proponents have received written approval from the Service that the biologist(s) is qualified to conduct work. The approved Service biologist shall keep a copy of the final biological opinion from the Service in their possession when on-site.
- c. A Service-approved biologist shall survey the work site within two weeks before the onset of activities for the California red-legged frog. If California red-legged frogs, tadpoles, or egg masses are found, the approved biologist shall contact the Service to determine if moving any of these life-stages is appropriate. In making this determination, the Service shall consider if an appropriate relocation site exists. If the Service approves moving the animals, the approved biologist shall be allowed sufficient time to move California red-legged frogs from the work site before activities begin. Only a Service-approved biologist shall participate in activities associated with the capture, handling, and monitoring of California red-legged frogs.
- d. For all ground disturbing activities involving vegetation removal, a Service-approved biologist familiar with the California red-legged frog shall conduct a pre-construction survey of the work area for these species within 24 hours prior to any vegetation removal or ground-disturbing activities. If any California red-legged frogs are found in the work area, construction activities shall not commence until a qualified biologist has verified that the species have left the work area. Both the CDFW and the Service shall be notified within 24 hours. Construction activities may not resume until approved by CDFW and the Service.
- e. If California red-legged frogs are not found within the proposed project footprint, immediately following the site survey the District shall install temporary fencing at the upper and lower limits of the construction footprint. The fencing shall be designed to impede California red-legged frogs from entering areas where construction will occur. The fencing shall be maintained and monitored by the applicant for the duration of the grading/construction period.
- f. A worker-training program and construction monitoring shall be performed by a qualified biologist during the initial ground-disturbing activities at each phase of the proposed project. The qualified biologist shall: (1) be familiar with both the California red-legged frog; (2) advise the construction crew that these species could be present on the site and vicinity and discuss their status and the procedure to follow if an individual is suspected to be present (i.e., that all work shall stop immediately in the vicinity of the individual until the species is accurately identified by the qualified biologist); and (3) monitor construction activity to assist the contractor in avoiding impacts to individuals of this species. If an individual California red-legged frog is discovered during initial ground-disturbing activity, all work in the vicinity of the observed frog shall stop and the Service and CDFW shall be contacted within 24 hours for guidance on how to proceed. All attendees shall sign an attendance sheet along with their printed name, company or agency, email address, and telephone number. The original

sign-in sheet shall be sent to the Service within seven (7) calendar days of the completion of the training.

- g. A Service-approved biologist shall be present at the work site until such time as removal of all California red-legged frogs is complete, instruction of workers, and initial habitat disturbance have been completed for the construction phase of the proposed project. After this time, the contractor or permittee shall designate a person to monitor on-site compliance with all minimization measures. The Service-approved biologist will ensure that this individual receives the training outlined above in conservation measure 20(f). The monitor and the Service-approved biologist shall have the authority to halt any action that might result in impacts that exceed the levels anticipated by the Corps and the Service during review of the proposed action. If work is stopped, the Corps, CDFW, and the Service shall be notified immediately by the Service-approved biologist or the on-site biological monitor.
- h. If any portion of the work area is to be temporarily dewatered by pumping, intakes shall be completely screened with wire mesh not larger than five millimeters to prevent California red-legged frogs from entering the pump system. A Service-approved biologist shall be present during initial dewatering activities. Upon completion of construction activities, any barriers to flow shall be removed in a manner that would allow flow to resume with the least disturbance to the substrate.
- i. Implement the following water quality protection measures as additional BMPs during project construction to protect aquatic life in and the water quality of the Alameda Creek channel:
 - i. Materials used for work in and below top-of-bank of the channel shall be non-toxic to aquatic life. Any concrete used in the channel shall be allowed to cure sufficiently (typically 30 to 60 calendar days unless an approved sealant is used) prior to contact with surface waters from the creek to avoid leaching of lime into receiving waters.
 - ii. All equipment refueling and maintenance shall occur outside the channel, and appropriate measures shall be implemented to prevent the discharge of fuels or other contaminants into the stream in the event of spills.
 - iii. An Erosion and Sediment Control Plan shall be developed, and standard erosion and water quality BMPs shall be implemented. After each phase of construction is complete, a final clean-up of the work site(s) shall include removal of all temporary exclusion fencing, flagging, sandbags, and other refuse generated by the proposed work.
 - iv. The project disturbance area shall be revegetated with an appropriate assemblage of native riparian, wetland and upland plant species suitable for the area. Details of the revegetation plantings and success criteria shall be stipulated in a Mitigation and Monitoring Plan.

- v. Concrete waste and water from curing operations shall be collected in washouts and shall be disposed of and not allowed into water courses.
- vi. Spill containment kits shall be maintained on-site at all times during construction operations and/or staging or fueling of equipment.
- vii. Dust control measures shall include use of water trucks and organic tackifiers to control dust in excavation and fill areas, covering temporary access road entrances and exits with rock (rocking), and covering of temporary stockpiles when weather conditions require.
- j. To the extent practicable, initial ground-disturbing activities will be avoided between November 1 and March 31 because that is the time period when California red-legged frogs are most likely to be moving through upland areas. When ground-disturbing activities must take place between November 1 and March 31, the Corps through the District will ensure that daily monitoring by a qualified biologist is completed for the California red-legged frog.
- k. Uneaten human food and trash attracts crows, ravens, coyotes, and other predators of the California red-legged frog. A litter control program will be instituted during each phase of the project. All workers will ensure their food scraps, paper wrappers, food containers, cans, bottles, and other trash are deposited in covered or closed trash containers. The trash containers will be removed from the project site at the end of each working day.
- l. No pets will be permitted at the project site, to avoid and minimize the potential for harassment, injury, and death of the California red-legged frog. However, the site is bordered by the existing regional trail along the levee tops where dogs and other pets are allowed on leash as part of historic practice and will continue once the proposed project is completed.
- m. No construction activities will occur in the creek channel during rain events or within 24 hours following a rain event. Prior to construction activities resuming, a qualified biologist will inspect the action area and all equipment/materials for the presence of California red-legged frogs. The animals will be allowed to move away from the project site of their own volition. A follow-up pre-construction survey will be performed as called for in this conservation measure if there is an unanticipated rain event.
- n. Night-time construction will be minimized or avoided during construction. Because dusk and dawn are often the times when the California red-legged frog is most actively moving and foraging, to the maximum extent practicable, earthmoving and construction activities will cease no less than 30 minutes before sunset and will not begin again prior to no less than 30 minutes after sunrise. Except when necessary for driver or pedestrian safety, to the maximum extent practicable, artificial lighting at the project site will be prohibited during the hours of darkness.
- o. Plastic monofilament netting (erosion control matting), loosely woven netting, or similar material in any form will not be used at the project site because California

red-legged frogs can become entangled and trapped in them. Any such material found on site will be immediately removed by a qualified biologist, construction personnel, or the applicant. Materials utilizing fixed weaves (strands cannot move), polypropylene, polymer or other synthetic materials will not be used.

- p. No firearms shall be allowed at the project site, to avoid and minimize the potential for harassment, injury, and death of the California red-legged frog.
- q. Dust control measures shall be implemented during construction, or when necessary in the opinion of the Service-approved biologist, the Service, CDFW, or their authorized agent. These measures shall consist of regular truck watering of construction access areas and disturbed soil areas with water or organic soil stabilizers to minimize airborne dust and soil particles generated from graded areas. Regular truck watering shall be a requirement of the construction contract. Watering guidelines for truck watering shall be established to avoid any excessive run-off that may flow into contiguous or adjacent areas containing potential habitat for the California red-legged frog.
- r. The Service-approved biologist(s) shall permanently remove any aquatic exotic wildlife species, such as bullfrogs and crayfish from the site, to the maximum extent possible.
- s. The District and Service-approved biologist(s) shall report any information to the Service about take or suspected take of listed wildlife species not exempted by the biological opinion. The Service will be notified via electronic mail and telephone within twenty-four (24) hours from the time the information is received by the applicant. Notification shall include the species, number of individuals, sex (if known), date, time, location of the incident or of the finding of a dead or injured animal, how the individual was taken, photographs of the specific animal, and names of the person who observed the take an/or found the animal.
- t. Each encounter with the California red-legged frog shall be treated on a case-by-case basis in coordination with the Service, but the general procedure is as follows: (1) the animal shall not be disturbed if it is not in danger; or (2) the animal shall be moved to a secure location if it is in danger. These procedures are further described below:
 - i. When a California red-legged frog is encountered in the action area, all activities which have the potential to result in the harassment, injury, or death of the individual shall be immediately halted. The Service-approved biologist shall then assess the situation in order to select a course of action that shall avoid or minimize adverse effects to the animal. To the maximum extent possible, contact with the frog shall be avoided and the applicant shall allow it to move out of the potentially hazardous situation to a secure location on its own volition. This procedure applies to situations where a California red-legged frog is encountered while it is moving to another location. It does not apply to animals that are uncovered or otherwise exposed or in areas where there is not sufficient adjacent habitat to support the species should the individual move away from the hazardous location.

- ii. California red-legged frogs that are in danger shall be relocated and released by the Service-approved biologist outside the construction area within the same riparian area or watershed. If relocation of the frog outside the fence is not feasible (i.e., there are too many individuals observed per day), the biologist shall relocate the animals to a Service pre-approved location. Prior to the initial ground disturbance, the applicant shall obtain approval of the relocation protocol from the Service in the event that a California re-legged frog is encountered and needs to be moved away from the site. Under no circumstances shall a California red-legged frog be released on a site unless the written permission of the landowner has been obtained by the applicant. The Service-approved biologist shall limit the duration of the handling and captivity of the California red-legged frog to the minimum amount of time necessary to complete the task. If the animal must be held in captivity, it shall be kept in a cool, dark, moist, aerated environment, such as a clean and disinfected bucket or plastic container with a damp sponge. The container used for holding or transporting the individual shall not contain any standing water.
- iii. The applicant shall immediately notify the Service once the California red-legged frog and the site are secure.

21. Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and California Clapper Rail

- a. A qualified biologist will (a) be retained by the District to monitor construction, and (b) will conduct mandatory contractor/worker awareness training for all personnel involved in project construction, addressing the proximity of the improvements to nearby marshland along Alameda Creek, regulated waters, and essential habitat for special-status species.
- b. The worker training program shall include a description of protected species and their habitat needs, any known occurrences in the project vicinity, an explanation of the status of these species and their protection under state and federal legislation, a description of nearby regulated waters and need to avoid these features, a list of measures being taken to completely avoid impacts to protected species during the work, and procedures to follow if a protected species is suspected to be present in the work area.
- c. Fact sheets containing the information presented during the worker training education program shall be provided to the project foreman and will be kept on-site for the duration of construction.
- d. The qualified biologist shall train the project foreman to serve as a biological monitor, making sure workers are following all required controls and inspecting the construction zone trenches or ditches for signs of protected species and maintaining the wildlife exclusion fencing or environmentally sensitive area fencing.
- e. The qualified biologist is someone knowledgeable about the biology and regulations regarding protected species and jurisdictional waters known or suspected to occur in or adjacent to the project, including California clapper

(Ridgway's) rail, California black rail, salt marsh common yellowthroat, salt marsh harvest mouse, western snowy plover, and Alameda song sparrow, among other salt and brackish water marsh-dependent species.

- f. Prior to any grading or other ground disturbing construction, a wildlife exclusion fencing shall be installed under the supervision of the qualified biologist to delineate the boundary of the work area from the sensitive nearby marshland and prevent small mammals from entering the work area. This shall be accomplished with the following controls and tasks.
- g. Before vegetation removal, the qualified biologist shall first conduct a thorough nest and small mammal search within areas of vegetation to be removed. If active small mammal nests with potential to be salt marsh harvest mouse nests are observed, a 50-foot buffer shall be established around the nest until the qualified biologist has determined that the young are independent of the nest. Vegetation shall then be removed using only hand tools to carefully remove vegetation down to bare ground.
 - i. The wildlife exclusion fencing may double as erosion control fencing, but must be buried a minimum of six inches below existing grade to prevent small mammals from digging underneath it.
 - ii. The wildlife exclusion fencing must be at least three (3) feet in height with vertical stakes installed on the roadway side of the fence at a minimum of six (6) foot intervals to prevent collapse for the duration of construction, and equipped with a minimum six (6) inch smooth, continuous top that small mammals cannot climb over, and preferably have a minimum three (3) inch fold directed away from the roadway that helps minimize the risk of small mammals climbing over the structure.
 - iii. The wildlife exclusion fencing will be setback a minimum of five (5) feet from intact salt marsh habitat to create a barren area that would discourage small mammal movement towards the wildlife exclusion fencing where cover is absent.
 - iv. Commercially available wildlife exclusion fencing is available which are equipped with a flange to prevent small mammals from climbing over them, such as E-Fence™ wildlife exclusion fence by ERTEC Environmental Systems, but should meet the height, buried depth and flange details.
 - v. The qualified biologist shall have the authority to direct field adjustments on the location, corrective design, and necessary maintenance of the fencing based on site-specific habitat conditions.
 - vi. The wildlife exclusion fencing shall remain in place for the duration of construction and repaired within 24 hours of the initial observance of damage. Work shall not continue within 300 feet of any damaged fencing until the wildlife exclusion fencing is repaired and the work zone surveyed

by the qualified biologist to ensure that no small mammals have entered and are at risk.

22. Western Snowy Plover

- a. Construction activities at the soil storage and wetland mitigation area may occur during the western snowy plover breeding season (March 1 -September 15) if they would occur at a minimum distance of 600 feet from an active western snowy plover nest or can be otherwise demonstrated that they would not interfere with nesting behavior based on further consultation and approval by the Service. In addition to preconstruction surveys to be conducted by a qualified biologist in accordance with conservation measures 10 and 14 above, the San Francisco Bay Bird Observatory shall be consulted to identify the current locations of active nests near Pond E3 at the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve prior to the commencement of work at the soil storage and wetland mitigation area and to confirm that no evidence of any active nesting activity has been observed along the southern edge of the pond.

23. Longfin Smelt

- a. Work in the Flood Control Channel will be limited to the dry season each year to the construction window from June 1 to October 31 when all life stages of longfin smelt are absent from the channel and areas immediately downstream.

Action Area

The action area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” For the proposed project, the action area encompasses the 72.2 acres of habitat within the proposed project footprint along a 5.6-mile-long reach of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel from the BART weir at the upstream end to 600 feet downstream of the UPRR bridge at the downstream end (Figure 1). Due to the indirect effects of the proposed project on sedimentation downstream, the action area also includes all of the tidal reach of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel from the downstream end of the proposed project footprint to San Francisco Bay. The action area also includes the 33-acre temporary soil storage site and 5-acre wetland creation site located approximately 1.4 miles southwest (downstream) of the most downstream end of the proposed project footprint (Figure 2).

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide

condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the action area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which determines all consequences to listed species that are caused by the proposed federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-federal activities in the action area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the listed species.

Status of the Species

California Red-legged Frog

Listing Status: The California red-legged frog was listed as a threatened species on May 23, 1996 (Service 1996). Critical habitat was designated for this species on April 13, 2006 (Service 2006), with revisions to the critical habitat designation published on March 17, 2010 (Service 2010). At that time, the Service recognized the taxonomic change from *Rana aurora draytonii* to *Rana draytonii* (Shaffer et al. 2010). The Service's *Recovery Plan for the California red-legged frog (Rana aurora draytonii)* (Recovery Plan) was published for the California red-legged frog on September 12, 2002 (Service 2002).

Description: The California red-legged frog is the largest native frog in the western United States (Wright and Wright 1949), ranging from 1.5 to 5.1 inches in length (Stebbins 2003). The abdomen and hind legs of adults are largely red, while the back is characterized by small black flecks and larger irregular dark blotches with indistinct outlines on a brown, gray, olive, or reddish background color. Dorsal spots usually have light centers (Stebbins 2003); dorsolateral folds are prominent on the back. The California red-legged frog is sexually dimorphic; the females are larger than the males (Dodd 2013a, b). California red-legged frog tadpoles range from 0.6 inch to 3.1 inches in length and the background color of the body is dark brown and yellow with darker spots (Storer 1925).

Current Status and Distribution: The historical range of the California red-legged frog extended from central Mendocino County and western Tehama County south in the California Coast Range to northern Baja California, Mexico, and in the Sierra Nevada/Cascade Ranges from Shasta County south to Madera County (Jennings and Hayes 1994). The species historically occurred from sea level to elevations of about 5,200 feet in 46 counties; however, currently the taxon is extant in 238 streams or drainages within only 22 counties, representing a loss of 70 percent of its former range (Service 2002). Isolated populations persist in several Sierra Nevada foothill locales and in Riverside County (Barry and Fellers 2013; Backlin et al. 2017; CDFW 2022; Gordon, R. and J. Bennett, pers. comm., 2017). The species is no longer considered extant in California's Central Valley due to significant declines caused by habitat modifications and exotic species (Fisher and Shaffer 1996). Currently, the California red-legged frog is widespread in the San Francisco Bay nine-county area (CDFW 2022). They are still locally abundant within the California coastal counties from Mendocino County to Los Angeles County and presumed extirpated in Orange and San Diego counties (CDFW 2022; Yang, D. and J. Martin, pers. comm., 2017; Gordon, R. and J. Bennett, pers. comm., 2017). Baja California represents the southernmost edge of the species' current range (Peralta-García et al. 2016).

Barry and Fellers (2013) conducted a comprehensive study to determine the current range of the California red-legged frog in the Sierra Nevada, concluding that it differs little from its historical range; however, the current Sierra Nevada populations appear to be small and tend to fluctuate. Since 1991, eleven California red-legged frog populations have been discovered or confirmed, including eight probable breeding populations (Barry and Fellers 2013; Mabe, J., pers. comm., 2017). Microsatellite and mitochondrial DNA analysis by Richmond et al. (2014) confirmed the Sierra Nevada populations of the California red-legged frog are genetically distinct from each other, as well as from other populations throughout the range of this species. The research concluded that the Sierra Nevada populations are persisting at low levels of genetic diversity and no contemporary gene flow across populations exist. On a larger geographic scale, range contraction has left a substantial gap between Sierra Nevada and Coast Range populations, similar to the gap separating the Southern California and Baja California populations (Richmond et al. 2014).

Habitat and Life History:

Habitat

The California red-legged frog generally breeds in still or slow-moving water associated with emergent vegetation, such as cattails, tules (hardstem bulrush), or overhanging willows (Storer 1925; Fellers 2005). Aquatic breeding habitat predominantly includes permanent water sources such as streams, marshes, and natural and manmade ponds in valley bottoms and foothills (Jennings and Hayes 1994; Bulger et al. 2003; Stebbins 2003). Since the 1850's, manmade ponds may actually supplement stream pool breeding habitat and can be capable of supporting large populations of this species. Breeding sites may hold water only seasonally, but sufficient water must persist at the beginning of the breeding season and into late summer or early fall for tadpoles to successfully complete metamorphosis. Breeding habitat does not include deep lacustrine water habitat (e.g., deep lakes and reservoirs 50 acres or larger in size) (Service 2010). Within the coastal lagoon habitats, salinity is a significant factor on embryonic mortality or abnormalities (Jennings and Hayes 1990). Jennings and Hayes (1990) conducted laboratory studies and field observations concluding salinity levels above 4.5 parts per thousand detrimentally affected the California red-legged frog embryos. Aquatic breeding habitat does not need to be available every year, but it must be available at least once within the frog's lifespan for breeding to occur (Service 2010).

Non-breeding aquatic habitat consists of shallow (non-lacustrine) freshwater features not suitable as breeding habitat, such as seasonal streams, small seeps, springs, and ponds that dry too quickly to support breeding. Non-breeding aquatic and riparian habitat is essential for providing the space, food, and cover necessary to sustain the California red-legged frog. Riparian habitat consists of vegetation growing nearby, but not typically in, a body of water on which it depends, and usually extends from the bank of a pond or stream to the margins of the associated floodplain (Service 2010). Adult California red-legged frogs may avoid coastal habitat with salinity levels greater than 6.5 parts per thousand (Jennings and Hayes 1990).

Cover and refugia are important habitat characteristic preferences for the species (Halstead and Kleeman 2017). Refugia may include vegetation, organic debris, animal burrows, boulders, rocks, logjams, industrial debris, or any other object that provides cover. Agricultural features such as watering troughs, spring boxes, abandoned sheds, or haystacks may also be utilized by the species. Incised stream channels with portions narrower and depths greater than 18 inches may also provide important summer sheltering habitat. During periods of high water flow,

California red-legged frogs are rarely observed; individuals may seek refuge from high flows in pockets or small mammal burrows beneath banks stabilized by shrubby riparian growth (Jennings and Hayes 1994). Accessibility to cover habitat is essential for the survival of California red-legged frogs within a watershed and can be a factor limiting frog population numbers and survival.

Breeding

In the Coast Range and at lower elevations, the California red-legged frog typically breeds between November and April (Storer 1925; Jennings and Hayes 1994; Fellers 2005). However, breeding phenology varies by location and across years, largely based on differences in climatic conditions (McHarry et al. 2019). At sites that routinely experience winter temperatures below freezing, the beginning of breeding is generally corresponded with the onset of spring's warmer air temperatures, such as in the Sierra Nevada where breeding typically occurs in late February and March (McHarry et al. 2019). Dependent on weather conditions, breeding in the Sierra Nevada can occur into late April (Barry 2002).

Females deposit their egg masses on emergent vegetation, floating on or near the surface of the water. The California red-legged frog is often a prolific breeder, laying eggs during or shortly after large rainfall events. Egg masses containing 300-4,000 eggs hatch after six to fourteen days (Storer 1925; Jennings and Hayes 1994; Fellers 2005). Historically, the California red-legged frog in the Sierra Nevada likely bred within stream pools, which tend to be small with limited forage, constraining the size and number of populations (Barry and Fellers 2013).

California red-legged frog tadpoles undergo metamorphosis three to seven months following hatching. Most males reach sexual maturity in two years, while it takes approximately three years for females (Jennings and Hayes 1985; Fellers 2005). Under favorable conditions, California red-legged frogs may live eight to ten years (Jennings et al. 1992). Of the various life stages, tadpoles likely experience the highest mortality rates; only one percent of each egg mass completes metamorphosis (Jennings et al. 1992).

Diet

The California red-legged frog has a variable diet that changes with each of its life history stages. The feeding habits of the early stages are likely similar to other ranids, whose tadpoles feed on algae, diatoms, and detritus by grazing on the surface of rocks and vegetation (Fellers 2005). Hayes and Tennant (1985) found invertebrates to be the most common food items of adult California red-legged frogs collected in southern California; however, they speculated that this was opportunistic and varied based on prey availability. Vertebrates, such as Pacific tree frogs (*Pseudacris regilla*) and California mice (*Peromyscus californicus*), represented over half of the prey mass eaten by larger frogs, although invertebrates were the most numerous food items. Feeding typically occurs along the shoreline and on the surface of the water; juveniles appear to forage during both daytime and nighttime, whereas adults appear to feed at night (Hayes and Tennant 1985).

Movement

California red-legged frogs do not have a distinct breeding migration (Fellers 2005), rather they may move seasonally from non-breeding pools or refugia to breeding pools. Some individuals remain at breeding sites year-round while others disperse to neighboring water features or moist

upland sites when breeding is complete and/or when breeding pools dry (Service 2002; Bulger et al. 2003; Fellers and Kleeman 2007; Tatarian and Tatarian 2008; Tatarian 2008). Studies in the several San Francisco Bay counties showed movements are typically along riparian corridors (Fellers and Kleeman 2007; Tatarian 2008). Although, some individuals, especially on rainy nights and in more mesic areas, travel without apparent regard to topography, vegetation type, or riparian corridors, and can move directly from one site to another through normally inhospitable habitats such as heavily grazed pastures or oak-grassland savannas (Bulger et al 2003).

California red-legged frogs show high site fidelity (Tatarian and Tatarian 2008) and typically do not move significant distances from breeding sites (Bulger et al. 2003; Fellers and Kleeman 2007; Tatarian and Tatarian 2008; Tatarian 2008). When traveling between aquatic sites, California red-legged frogs typically travel less than 0.31 miles (Fellers and Kleeman 2007; Tatarian and Tatarian 2008), although they have been documented to move more than two miles in Santa Cruz County (Bulger et al. 2003). Various studies have found that the frogs typically do not make terrestrial forays further than 200 feet from aquatic habitat (Bulger et al. 2003; Fellers and Kleeman 2007; Tatarian and Tatarian 2008; Tatarian 2008). Upland movements are typically associated with precipitation events and usually last for one to four days (Tatarian 2008).

Threats: Factors associated with declining populations of the California red-legged frog throughout its range include degradation and loss of habitat through agriculture, urbanization, mining, overgrazing, recreation, timber harvesting, non-native species, impoundments, water diversions, erosion and siltation altering upland and aquatic habitat, degraded water quality, use of pesticides, and introduced predators (Service 2002, 2010). Urbanization often leaves isolated habitat fragments and creates barriers to frog dispersal.

Non-native species pose a major threat to the recovery of California red-legged frogs. Several researchers have noted the decline and eventual local disappearance of California and northern red-legged frogs in systems supporting bullfrogs (Jennings and Hayes 1990; Twedt 1993), red swamp crayfish, signal crayfish, and several species of warm water fish including sunfish, goldfish, common carp, and mosquitofish (Moyle 1976; Barry 1992; Hunt 1993; Fisher and Shaffer 1996). The decline of the California red-legged frog due to these non-native species has been attributed to predation, competition, and reproduction interference (Twedt 1993; Bury and Whelan 1984; Storer 1933; Emlen 1977; Kruse and Francis 1977; Jennings and Hays 1990; Jennings 1993).

Chytridiomycosis, an infectious disease caused by the chytrid fungus, *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (*Bd*), has been found to adversely affect amphibians globally (Davidson et al. 2003; Lips et al. 2006). While *Bd* prevalence in wild amphibian populations in California is unknown (Fellers et al. 2011), chytrid is expected to be widespread throughout much of the California red-legged frog's range. The chytrid fungus has been documented within the California red-legged frog populations at Point Reyes National Seashore, two properties in Santa Clara County, Yosemite National Park, Hughes Pond, Sailor Flat, Big Gun Diggings, and Spivey Pond (Padgett-Flohr and Hopkins 2010; Tatarian and Tatarian 2010; Fellers et al. 2011; Barry and Fellers 2013). However, no chytrid-related mortality has been reported in these populations, suggesting that California red-legged frogs are less vulnerable to the pathogenic effects of chytrid infection than other amphibian species (Tatarian and Tatarian 2010; Barry and Fellers 2013; Fellers et al. 2017). While chytrid infection may not directly lead to mortality in California red-legged frogs, Padgett-Flohr (2008) states that this infection may reduce overall fitness and could lead to long-term effects. Therefore, it is difficult to estimate the full extent and risk of chytridiomycosis to the California red-legged frog populations.

Recovery Plan: The Recovery Plan identifies eight recovery units (Service 2002). The goal of the Recovery Plan is to protect the long-term viability of all extant populations within each recovery unit. Within each recovery unit, delineated core areas, designed to protect metapopulations, represent contiguous areas of moderate to high California red-legged frog densities. The management strategy identified within this Recovery Plan will allow for the recolonization of habitats within and adjacent to core areas naturally subjected to periodic localized extinctions, thus assuring the long-term survival and recovery of California red-legged frogs.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the action area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the action area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the action area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the environmental baseline.

Historically, flooding occurred in the lower reaches of Alameda Creek. To address the flooding issue, the Corps designed and constructed the 12-mile reach of flood control conveyance channel (Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel) with a 170 to 310 foot-wide, flat-bottom trapezoidal earthen channel and levees between Niles Canyon and San Francisco Bay. The flood control channel was completed in 1972 and was transferred to the District to maintain in accordance with the O&M Manual. The maintenance responsibilities include ensuring channel and levee structural integrity, erosion control, debris and periodic sediment removal from the channel.

Since construction of the channel, a meandering low-flow channel (active channel) has naturally established and persists between sediment-removal episodes. It is generally located towards the center of the 170 to 310 foot-wide flat-bottom channel, except at some locations where the active channel hugs the toe of the levee's slopes. At other locations, there are secondary offshoots that often result in braided reaches. The 15-25 foot-wide active channel persists throughout the entire reach below the BART weir into the stable tidal zone near the downstream end of the proposed project limits.

The flood control channel was constructed on a relatively flat alluvial floodplain, resulting in immediate sediment deposition as the creek emerges out of the hills to the east. Consequently, within 10 years of channel construction, sedimentation became a major concern requiring periodic removal to maintain the channel design capacity in accordance with the Corps' O&M Manual. To address the recurring sedimentation problem beginning in 1975, the District would excavate the sediment and off-haul to a disposal site. The sediment removal occurs on an average cycle of 10 years.

The 72.2-acre proposed project footprint consists of a 5.6-mile-long reach of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel that is entirely surrounded by urban areas composed primarily of medium to high density housing (Figure 1). The banks of the east to west flowing channel reach within the project limits are steep and armored with rock riprap. The Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel maintenance access roads are located atop of both levees. These access roads also double as pedestrian and bicycle trails managed by the East Bay Regional Park District. Planted

trees and shrubs line portions of the upper banks. The upland terrain beyond the channel elevation ranges from 47 feet above sea level at the upstream end to 10 feet above sea level at the downstream limit.

Alameda Creek drains the Coastal Range east of San Francisco Bay. Alameda Creek's headwaters are on the southwestern flank of Mount Hamilton in Santa Clara County. It flows to the northwest for approximately 25 miles, then to the west through Niles Canyon for approximately 5 miles in a mostly natural configuration, then discharges into the District's Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel at Mission Boulevard crossing in the City of Fremont. The Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel extends approximately 12 miles between Mission Boulevard and the San Francisco Bay. Numerous storm drains and side channels carry stormwater and urban runoff into the channel.

The Alameda Creek watershed flows are regulated by several dams, reservoirs, and GC structures. The watershed collects water from Livermore Valley to the northeast, and Mount Hamilton in eastern Santa Clara County. There is a continuous subsurface flow of water in the streambed where bedrock is near the surface.

Vegetation types along the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel corridor through the action area are characterized as riparian, ruderal, non-native annual grasslands, fresh emergent vegetation, and riverine. Brackish water marsh vegetation is present in a tidally influenced portion of the creek downstream of the UPRR bridge. The bank tops of the channel have maintenance access roads on both sides along the top of the levees. The mid to upper banks consist of rock slope protection with sparse non-native grasses and ruderal species. Between the toe of slope and the lower bank, non-native grasslands are the dominant plant community. Vegetation in the channel consists of emergent wetland vegetation that has a mix of native and non-native species.

Sparse, fragmented bands of planted trees line the upper banks along the outer edges of the flood-control access roads in the action area and are classified as riparian given their occurrence on the channel banks. The dominant trees are non-native landscape species, primarily eucalyptus, *Myoporum* species, Peruvian pepper tree, acacia, and pines. Coast live oaks are present in small numbers. In most cases, the trees are set back from the channel edge and provide no shade over the water. Understory plants along the riparian corridor consist mainly of non-native grasses and occasional landscape shrubs.

Ruderal habitats are present within the action area from the outer edges of the access roads to the base of the rock slope protection lining the upper banks. Plants in the ruderal habitat are primarily non-native grasses including slender oats, wild oats, and ripgut brome.

Non-native annual grasslands can be found throughout the action area along the mid and lower banks of the creek. Non-native plant species found in the annual grasslands in the action area include slender oats, wild oats, ripgut brome, ryegrass, and weedy forbs including wild radish, Italian thistle, rough cocklebur, fennel, and bristly ox's tongue.

The Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel is inundated during periods of heavy rainfall during the winter months but recedes rapidly during dry periods. This, coupled with the frequent replenishment from runoff, allows the freshwater emergent wetland conditions to persist throughout the year. Freshwater emergent wetland vegetation observed in the action area consists

of native species such as occasional young willow plants, cattail, and California bulrush. Exotic wetland species included poison hemlock, perennial pepperweed, and pennyroyal, among others.

Brackish water emergent wetlands begin to appear approximately 300 feet downstream of the UPRR bridge, although some salinity contributing to suitable habitat conditions for brackish water species may extend up to the UPRR bridge. Further downstream, well below the project footprint, the brackish water marsh gives way to salt marsh habitat, dominated by pickleweed, California cordgrass, and other salt marsh species.

Temporary Soil Storage/Wetland Creation Site

The 33-acre soil disposal area and 5-acre wetland mitigation area are located west of Union City Boulevard and north of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel approximately 1.4 miles southwest (downstream) of the most downstream end of the proposed project footprint (Figure 2). The soil disposal area and wetland mitigation area consist of disturbed open fields bordered by the north flood control levee of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel to the south and diked baylands that are used for grazing and hay production. The fields are routinely disked and generally devoid of vegetative cover, with the exception of narrow drainages between the tilled fields that support a cover dominated by pickleweed and other wetland indicator species.

The temporary soil storage/wetland creation site is bordered on the west by diked wetlands within the CDFW's Eden Landing Ecological Reserve, part of the South Bay Salt Pond Restoration Project. To the south is the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel and levee that is part of the Alameda Creek Regional Trail. Residential uses, farm lands, and a school are located further east of the site. The site consists of former San Francisco Bay margin that was cut off from tidal influence when the new Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel was created. As such, it has soils, topography, and potential hydrologic regime to support wetlands. In addition, it was selected due to proximity to the impact area, similarity of habitat, and ownership and management opportunities. Most of the site is largely void of natural vegetation, although the inboard side of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel levee supports limited pickleweed mats and a combination of native and non-native trees. The vegetation along the levee consists primarily of weedy species, including several invasive plant species. The site is currently cultivated and disked for hay production.

The site is bounded by five drainage ditches. Dominant plant species supported in the drainage ditch habitat include pickleweed, alkali heath, and common mallow. The drainage ditches have wetland indicator traits such as oxidized rhizospheres along living roots, hydric soils, obligate or facultative wetland vegetation, and salt crusts. Three of the drainage ditches connect to existing seasonal wetland habitat adjacent the westernmost parcel. This wetland is connected to a channel that passes through the underside of the main levee with a possible culvert connection which likely drains into the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel. This feature is seasonally inundated. Although the site is farmed, the drainage ditches are not plowed or disked and support pickleweed mats. The ditches likely receive water from direct precipitation and subsurface flow.

Non-native blue gum occurs along the inboard side of the levee along the southern boundary of the site. This is beyond the existing fence of the parcels. Blue gum is the dominant overstory along this area while oak trees are interspersed throughout the blue gum. The understory of the mixed blue gum and oak grove consists of non-native grasses, weedy plant species, bay-margin vegetation that is primarily pickleweed, woody debris and leaf litter.

California Red-legged Frog

Due to its location in a highly urbanized environment, the action area provides a narrow corridor of marginal quality non-breeding aquatic and upland dispersal habitat for the California red-legged frog throughout the 72.2-acre (5.6-mile-long) proposed project footprint of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel except for the most downstream 300 feet where the higher salinities of the brackish marsh habitat likely exclude the California red-legged frog. California red-legged frogs are also absent from the tidally influenced reaches of the action area downstream of the proposed project footprint due to the higher salinities. The California red-legged frog is also absent from the 33-acre temporary soil storage site and 5-acre wetland creation site (Figure 2) due to the higher salinities and distance from suitable freshwater habitat.

California red-legged frogs are unlikely to breed within the action area due to the presence of non-native predatory fish and fast-moving winter and occasional spring flows that would scour any egg masses. The upstream end of the action area is adjacent to the Quarry Lakes Regional Recreation Area; however, the deep quarry lakes are unlikely to support breeding California red-legged frogs due to the presence of non-native predatory fish and bullfrogs, recreation, and the lack of shallow water habitat with emergent vegetation. However, since the action area is within 1.1 miles downstream of higher quality occupied habitat for the California red-legged frog, the Service cannot discount the potential for the California red-legged frog to infrequently disperse from or be washed down from higher quality habitat upstream.

The nearest California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB) occurrences of the California red-legged frog to the action area are (CDFW 2022):

1. One adult California red-legged frog observed in a ditch 1.7 miles north-northwest of the action area in 1999 (CNDDDB occurrence number 350);
2. One juvenile California red-legged frog observed in a stock pond at Vargas Ranch 3.3 miles east-northeast (upstream) of the action area in 2000 (CNDDDB occurrence number 569);
3. Two California red-legged frog larvae observed in a stock pond at Vargas Ranch 3.8 miles east-northeast (upstream) of the action area in 2000 (CNDDDB occurrence number 581);
4. One California red-legged frog larva observed in a stock pond at Vargas Ranch 3.7 miles east-northeast (upstream) of the action area in 2000 (CNDDDB occurrence number 568); and
5. Nine adult California red-legged frogs observed in a stock pond 4.0 miles east-southeast of the action area in 2012 (CNDDDB occurrence number 1565).

The action area is located in the South and East San Francisco Bay recovery unit for the California red-legged frog (Service 2002). The action area is not located within a core area for the California red-legged frog; the nearest core area is the East San Francisco Bay core area located 1.1 miles east (upstream) of the action area (Service 2002).

Based on the known occurrence of the California red-legged frog within the frog's 2-mile dispersal distance of the action area and the availability of suitable non-breeding aquatic and upland habitat within the action area, the Service believes the California red-legged frog is likely

to disperse, forage, and shelter in the action area. However, due to the action area occurring within a highly urbanized area with no suitable breeding habitat nearby, the Service believes that the California red-legged frog only infrequently disperses through the action area.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The proposed project will result in the permanent loss of 1.67 acres and the temporary disturbance of 70.53 acres of non-breeding aquatic and adjacent upland dispersal, foraging, and sheltering habitat for the California red-legged frog along approximately 5.6 miles of the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel. Habitat will be permanently lost due to the placement of rock scour protection and levee toe protection. All temporarily disturbed habitat will be restored under a Service-approved restoration and monitoring plan with success criteria. The proposed project is expected to benefit the California red-legged frog in the long-term through increasing aquatic habitat complexity and pooling within the Alameda Creek Flood Control Channel. Additionally, the proposed project will reduce the need for future maintenance work and sediment excavation in the creek that could injure or kill California red-legged frogs.

California red-legged frogs could be injured or killed if they were run over by heavy equipment or crushed during sediment excavation and placement of rock riprap, boulders, and large woody debris. California red-legged frogs could also desiccate or be preyed upon due to the temporary removal of vegetative cover. The potential for injuring or killing California red-legged frogs will be minimized by: (1) a qualified biologist conducting preconstruction surveys; (2) any California red-legged frogs observed within the work area will be safely relocated out of the work area by a qualified biologist; (3) all proposed project construction staff will be trained by a qualified biologist in the identification of the California red-legged frog and the implementation of the conservation measures; (4) a qualified biologist will be onsite until initial habitat disturbance is completed; (5) wildlife exclusion fencing will be installed to prevent California red-legged frogs from entering the work area; (6) pump intakes used for dewatering will be screened with wire mesh not larger than five millimeters; (7) work will be restricted to the dry season; and (8) no work will occur at nighttime or within 24 hours following a rain event when the California red-legged frog is most likely to disperse through the work area.

The potential for degradation of aquatic habitat for the California red-legged frog will be minimized through dewatering the work area prior to construction, the implementation of water quality BMPs and a spill prevention plan, and restricting work to the dry season.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the California red-legged frog, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California red-legged frog. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual California red-legged frogs; (2) the vast majority of the effects will be temporary; (3) all habitat disturbed by the proposed project will be restored; (4) no suitable breeding habitat will be disturbed; (5) non-breeding aquatic habitat will be enhanced within the action area through an increase in aquatic habitat complexity, large woody debris, and pooling; and (6) few California red-legged frogs are likely to occur within the action area.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps or the District must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take*California Red-legged Frog*

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual California red-legged frogs will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of California red-legged frogs that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. The non-lethal harm and capture of all adult and juvenile California red-legged frogs within the 1.67 acres of habitat permanently removed and the 70.53 acres of habitat temporarily disturbed within the 5.6-mile-long proposed project footprint.
2. The injury or mortality of one (1) adult or juvenile California red-legged frog.

Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take of the California red-legged frog associated with the Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3 will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the species.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California red-legged frog resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed conservation measures. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize incidental take of the California red-legged frog:

- 1) All conservation measures, as described in the biological assessment and restated here in the Description of the Proposed Action section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. The Corps shall include full implementation and adherence to the conservation measures as a condition of any permit or contract issued for the proposed project.

Monitoring:

- a. For those components of the action that will result in habitat degradation or modification whereby incidental take in the form of harm is anticipated, the Corps or the District shall provide a precise accounting of the total acreage of habitat impacted to the Service after completion of construction.
- b. The Corps or the District shall immediately contact the Service's Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office (SFWO) at (916) 414-6623 to report direct encounters between listed species and project workers and their equipment whereby incidental take in the form of harassment, harm, injury, or death occurs. If the encounter occurs after normal working hours, the Corps or the District shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day. When injured or killed individuals of the listed species are found, the Corps or the District shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals section below.
- c. For those components of the action that will require the capture and relocation of any listed species, the Corps or the District shall immediately contact the SFWO at (916) 414-6623 to report the action. If capture and relocation need to occur after normal working hours, the Corps or the District shall contact the SFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day.
- d. Annual reports shall be provided to the Service each year during the proposed project period documenting with photographs the successful restoration of all habitats temporarily disturbed within the action area, any observations of listed species within the action area, and the number of each listed species relocated.
- e. A post-project completion report shall be provided to the Service documenting with photographs the successful restoration of all habitats temporarily disturbed within the action area and any observations of listed species within the action area.
- f. All sightings of listed species shall be submitted to CDFW's CNDDDB.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals:

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Coast Bay Division Supervisor of the SFWO at (916) 414-6623.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) The Corps should include in their permits the control of non-native bullfrogs, non-native fish, non-native crayfish, and other invasive species and predators within suitable breeding habitat for the California red-legged frog.
- 2) The Corps should include in their permits the restoration, preservation, and management in perpetuity under a Service-approved long-term management plan suitable aquatic breeding habitat and surrounding upland habitat for the California red-legged frog.
- 3) The Corps should include in their permits in suitable tidal marsh habitat the control of invasive plant species and restoration of high-tide refugia habitat for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.
- 4) The Corps should include in their permits the control of nonnative mammal predators of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and western snowy plover.
- 5) The Corps should report sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species to the CNDDDB of the CDFW. A copy of the reporting form and a topographic map clearly marked with the location the animals were observed also should be provided to the Service.
- 6) The Corps should include in their permits the Service's conservation recommendations for the western population of the Federal candidate monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*) available at: <https://xerces.org/publications/planning-management/western-monarch-butterfly-conservation-recommendations>
 - a. Native, insecticide-free milkweed species (*Asclepias* species) (with a focus on early-emerging milkweed species (e.g., *Asclepias vestita*, *A. californica*, *A. eriocarpa*, *A. cordifolia*, *A. erosa*)) should be included in the planting palette in restoration plans within suitable breeding habitat in the San Francisco Bay Area and Central Valley that is more than 5 miles from monarch butterfly overwintering habitat along the coast and San Francisco Bay.
 - b. Suitable native, insecticide-free nectar plants (with a focus on early-emerging flowering plants that are available to monarchs from January-April) should be included in the planting palette in all restoration plans in suitable habitat in the San Francisco Bay Area and Central Valley.
 - c. Milkweed larval host plants for the monarch butterfly should be flagged and avoided. If avoidance of milkweed larval host plants is not feasible, then the milkweed plants should be removed between November 1 and March 15 within early breeding habitat in the San Francisco Bay Area and Central Valley when monarchs are less likely to be in the area. Each year and site are different, so when possible, please consider surveying milkweed plants for the early life stages of monarchs prior to removing or disturbing them.
 - d. Management activities that could disturb monarch butterflies near overwintering sites along the Pacific Coast and San Francisco Bay should occur between March 15 and September 15 when the monarch is less likely to occur at the overwintering sites.
 - e. Avoid herbicide application on blooming flowers. Apply herbicides during young plant phases, when plants are more responsive to treatment, and when monarch

butterflies and other pollinators are less likely to be nectaring on the plants. Whenever possible, use targeted application herbicide methods, avoid large-scale broadcast applications, and take precautions to limit off-site movement of herbicides (e.g., drift from wind and discharge from surface water flows).

- f. Report milkweed and monarch observations for all life stages, including breeding butterflies, to the Monarch Milkweed Mapper (<https://www.monarchmilkweedmapper.org/>) or via the project portal in the iNaturalist smartphone app (<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/western-monarch-milkweed-mapper>).

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project Phases 1-3. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16(a), reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the federal agency or by the Service where discretionary federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law, and:

- 1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- 2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- 3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or
- 4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Joseph Terry, Senior Biologist (joseph_terry@fws.gov) or at (916) 943-6721 or Ryan Olah, Coast Bay Division Supervisor (ryan_olah@fws.gov), at (916) 414-6623.

Sincerely,

Michael Fris
Field Supervisor

ec:

U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, San Francisco, California
Kim Squires, San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California
Dan Logan, National Marine Fisheries Service, Santa Rosa, California
Gary Stern, National Marine Fisheries Service, Santa Rosa, California

Brenda Blinn, California Department of Fish and Wildlife, Fairfield, California

Marcia Grefsrud, California Department of Fish and Wildlife, Fairfield, California

Jim Martin, Environmental Collaborative, Emeryville, California

Jim Browne, Alameda County Public Works Agency, Hayward, California

Moses Tsang, Alameda County Public Works Agency, Hayward, California

Brian Wines, San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board, Oakland, California

LITERATURE CITED

- Alameda County Flood Control District (District). 2022. Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project, City of Fremont, Alameda County, California Biological Assessment for USFWS Consultation. October 2022. Hayward, California. 101 pp. plus appendices.
- Backlin, A.R., J.Q. Richmond, E.A. Gallegos, C.K. Christensen, and R.N. Fisher. 2017. An extirpated lineage of a threatened frog species resurfaces in southern California. *Oryx*: 1–5.
- Barry, S. 1992. Letter to Marvin L. Plenert, Regional Director, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon, regarding proposed listing.
- Barry, S. 2002. Dobbins and Cottage/Deadwood Watersheds, Plumas National Forest, Herpetological Surveys, 2001-2002. Department of Zoology, University of California, Davis
- Barry, S.J. and G.M. Fellers. 2013. History and status of the California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*) in the Sierra Nevada, California, USA. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 8(2): 456-502.
- Bulger, J.B., N.J. Scott Jr., and R.B. Seymour. 2003. Terrestrial activity and conservation of adult California red-legged frogs *Rana aurora draytonii* in coastal forests and grasslands. *Biological Conservation* 110(2003): 85–95.
- Bury, R.B. and J.A. Whelan. 1984. Ecology and management of the bullfrog. Fish and Wildlife Resource Publication 155.
- California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW). 2022. California Natural Diversity Database. RAREFIND. Natural Heritage Division, Sacramento, California.
- Davidson, E.W., M. Parris, J.O. Collins, J.E. Longcore, A.P. Pessier, and J. Brunner. 2003. Pathogenicity and transmission of *Chytridiomycosis* in tiger salamanders (*Ambystoma tigrinum*). *Copeia* 2003(3): 601-607.
- Dodd, C.K. 2013a. Frogs of the United States and Canada. Volume 1. John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, Maryland.
- Dodd, C.K. 2013b. Frogs of the United States and Canada. Volume 2. John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, Maryland.
- Emlen, S.T. 1977. “Double clutching” and its possible significance in the bullfrog. *Copeia* 1977(4): 749-751.
- Fellers, G. 2005. *Rana draytonii* Baird and Girard, 1852b California red-legged frog. Pages 552-554 in M. Lannoo (editor). Amphibian declines the conservation status of United States species. University of California Press. Berkeley, California.
- Fellers, G.M., and P.M. Kleeman. 2007. California Red-Legged Frog (*Rana draytonii*) Movement and Habitat Use: Implications for Conservation. *Journal of Herpetology* 41: 276-286.

- Fellers, G.M., R.A. Cole, D.M. Reintz, and P.M. Kleeman. 2011. Amphibian chytrid fungus (*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*) in coastal and montane California, USA Anurans. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 6(3): 383-394.
- Fellers, G.M., P.M. Fleeman, D.A.W. Miller, and B.J. Halstead. 2017. Population Trends, Survival, and Sampling Methodologies for a Population of *Rana draytonii*. *Journal of Herpetology* 51(4): 567-573.
- Fisher, R.N. and H.B. Shaffer. 1996. The decline of amphibians in California's Great Central Valley. *Conservation Biology* 10(5): 1387-1397.
- Halstead, B.J. and P.M. Kleeman. 2017. Frogs on the Beach: Ecology of California red-legged frogs (*Rana draytonii*) in Coastal Dune Drainages. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 12: 127-140.
- Hayes, M.P. and M.R. Tennant. 1985. Diet and feeding behavior of the California red-legged frog *Rana aurora draytonii* (Ranidae). *The Southwestern Naturalist* 30(4):601-605.
- Hunt, L. 1993. Letter to Marvin L. Plenert, Regional Director, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Portland, Oregon, regarding proposed listing.
- Jennings, M.R. 1993. Letter to Peter C. Sorensen, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Sacramento, California.
- Jennings, M.R. and M.P. Hayes. 1985. Pre-1900 overharvest of California red-legged frogs (*Rana aurora draytonii*): The inducement for bullfrog (*Rana catesbeiana*) introduction. *Herpetological Review* 31(1): 94-103.
- Jennings, M.R. and M.P. Hayes. 1990. Final report of the status of the California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) in the Pescadero Marsh Natural Preserve. Final report prepared for the California Department of Parks and Recreation, Sacramento, California through Agreement (4-823-9018). Department of Herpetology, California Academy of Sciences, Golden Gate Park, San Francisco, California. 30 pages.
- Jennings, M.R. and M.P. Hayes. 1994. Amphibian and reptile species of special concern in California. California Department of Fish and Game, Rancho Cordova, California.
- Jennings, M.R., M.P. Hayes, and D.C. Holland. 1992. A petition to the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service to place the California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*) and the western pond turtle (*Clemmys marmorata*) on the List of Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants. 21 pages.
- Kruse, K.C. and M.G. Francis. 1977. A predation deterrent in larvae of the bullfrog, *Rana catesbeiana*. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* 106(3): 248-252.
- Lips, K.R., F. Brem, R. Brenes, J.D. Reeve, R.A. Alford, J. Voyles, C. Carey, L. Livo, A.P. Pessier and J.P. Collins. 2006. Emerging infectious disease and the loss of biodiversity in a Neotropical amphibian community. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 103(9): 3165-3170.

- McHarry, K., J. Abbott, B. Hudgens, M. Harbert, and L. Gordon. 2019. Red-legged frog (*Rana aurora and Rana draytonii*) research report 2018. Institute for Wildlife Studies, Blue Lakes, California. 27 pp.
- Moyle, P.B. 1976. Fish introductions in California: a history and impact of native fishes. *Biological Conservation* 9(1): 101-118.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2015. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2017. September 24, 2015. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2016. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2016. November 30, 2016. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2018a. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2017. January 23, 2018. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2018b. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2018. November 28, 2018. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2020. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2019. January 13, 2020. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2021. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2020. February 1, 2021. Oakland, California.
- Olofson Environmental Inc. 2022. California Ridgway's Rail Surveys for the San Francisco Estuary Invasive Spartina Project 2021. January 31, 2022. Oakland, California.
- Padgett-Flohr, G. 2008. Pathogenicity of *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* in two threatened California amphibians: *Rana draytonii* and *Ambystoma californiense*. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 3(2): 182-191.
- Padgett-Flohr, G.E. and R.L. Hopkins, II. 2010. Landscape epidemiology of *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* in central California. *Ecography* 33: 688–697.
- Peralta-García, A., B.D. Hollingsworth, J.Q. Richmond, J.H. Valdez-Villavicentio, G. Ruiz-Campos, R. N. Fisher, P. Cruz-Hernandez, P. Galina-Tessaro. 2016. Status of the California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*) in the state of Baja California, México. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 11(1): 168-180.
- Questa Engineering Corporation. 2022. Habitat Mitigation and Monitoring Plan Lower Alameda Creek Restoration Project- Phases 1 and 2 Alameda County, California. June 2022. Prepared for Alameda County Flood Control and Water Conservation District, Hayward, California. 14 pp. plus appendix.
- Richmond, J.O., A.R. Backlin, P.J. Tatarian, B.G. Solvesky, R.N. Fisher. 2014. Population declines lead to replicate patterns of internal range structure at the tips of the distribution of the California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*). *Biological Conservation* 172: 128-137.

- Shaffer, H.B., G.M. Fellers, S.R. Voss, C. Oliver, and G.B. Pauley. 2010. Species boundaries, phylogeography, and conservation genetics of the red-legged frog (*Rana aurora/draytonii*) complex. *Molecular Ecology* 13: 2667-2677.
- Stebbins, R.C. 2003. A field guide to western reptiles and amphibians. Houghton Mifflin. Boston, Massachusetts
- Storer, T.I. 1925. A synopsis of the Amphibia of California. University of California Publications in Zoology 27: 1-342.
- Storer, T.I. 1933. Frogs and their commercial use. California Department of Fish and Game 19(3): 203-213.
- Tatarian, T.J. and G. Tatarian. 2008. California red-legged frog telemetry study; Hughes Pond, Plumas National Forest. Annual Report, Option Year 3 to: U. S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 2800 Cottage Way, Sacramento, CA and U.S. Forest Service, Plumas National Forest, 875 Mitchell Avenue, Oroville, CA.
- Tatarian, T.J. and G. Tatarian. 2010. Chytrid Infection of *Rana draytonii* in the Sierra Nevada, California, USA. *Herpetological Review* 41(3): 325-327.
- Tatarian, P.J. 2008. Movement patterns of California red-legged frogs (*Rana draytonii*) in an inland California environment. *Herpetological Conservation and Biology* 3(2): 155-169.
- Twedt, B. 1993. A comparative ecology of *Rana aurora* Baird and Girard and *Rana catesbeiana* Shaw at Freshwater Lagoon, Humboldt County, California. Master of Science thesis. Humboldt State University, Arcata, California. 53 pages plus appendix.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service). 1996. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; determination of threatened status for the California red-legged frog. Federal Register 61: 25813-25833.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service). 2002. Recovery plan for the California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*). Portland, Oregon. 173 pages.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service). 2006. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; designation of critical habitat for the California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*), and special rule exemption associated with final listing for existing routine ranching activities; final rule. Federal Register 71(71): 19244-19346.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service). 2010. Endangered and threatened wildlife and plants; revised designation of critical habitat for California red-legged frog; final rule. Federal Register 75: 12815-12959.
- Wright, A.H. and A.A. Wright. 1949. Handbook of frogs and toads in the United States and Canada. Comstock Publishing, Ithaca, New York.

PERSONAL COMMUNICATION

Gordon, R. and J. Bennett. Electronic mail communication from Rebecca Gordon and Jesse Bennett, Service, Carlsbad FWO, to Valerie Hentges, Service, Sacramento FWO, dated October 12, 2017.

Mabe, J. 2017. Phone conversation from Jeff Mabe, U.S. Forest Service, Eldorado National Forest, to Ian Vogel, Service, Sacramento FWO, dated June 6, 2017.

Yang, D. and J. Martin. Electronic mail communication from Dou-Shuan Yang and Jacob Martin, Service, Ventura FWO, to Valerie Hentges, Service, Sacramento FWO, dated July 5, 2017.